

THE IMPORTANCE OF COMPETENCE AND TALENT MANAGEMENT IN INCREASING CREATIVE THINKING INNOVATION TO PRODUCE QUALITY PERFORMANCE AT PT BHINNEKA TEKNO SEJATI

INDRI GUSLINA

Dosen STIM Budi Bakti. Email: in.guslina@gmail.com

Abstract

Innovation is needed by every human resource to be able to think creatively in producing quality performance in order to realize the vision of the organization. Of course, innovation is supported by competence and talent management. The application of creativity in the form of new and/or different ideas/ideas that can make a form/model/activity/product/service simpler, easier, more efficient and more effective. Human resource development strategy Employee management policies that are integrated with organizational / company strategies and can be used to encourage organizational culture so that employees have values and quality competencies that are in accordance with the needs of achieving vision, mission and goals and become a source of competitive advantage for individuals and companies / organizations. Competence is reflected in performance so that good performance is optimal performance. The performance of these employees is one of the capitals for the organization to achieve its goals so that employee performance is something that should be considered by the leader of the organization. Competencies describe what people do at work at various levels and detail the standards of each level, identify the characteristics, knowledge and skills required by individuals that enable them to carry out responsibilities effectively so as to achieve professional standards in work and cover all aspects/indicators, namely performance management records, specific skills and knowledge, attitudes, communication, application and resource development human. Talent Management is one of the HR management methods developed to find, manage, develop and retain employees who are prepared as future leaders in order to support the achievement of the vision, mission, and strategy of the organization. which is very good. One of the things that companies do in order to compete with other companies is creativity and innovation. Through creative and innovative employees, companies can create bright ideas about the best products and services.

Keywords: Competency, Talent Management, Innovation, Creative, Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Employee competence can be done with the main goal is to highlight the quantity and quality of work and the use of working hours used in carrying out work. This is based on the consideration that an employee does his work not only profit-oriented or profit-oriented but also prioritizes the quality of service to the community so that the quantity and quality of work and the use of working hours are the most important and top priority for employees to carry out work optimally and successfully, where the use of resources is expected to be relatively small but the results obtained are relatively large (Putro & Sahban, 2020). Every day, every time we meet other people, with different employee backgrounds we see different behaviors from the habits we do which means different understanding. We see, hear, smell, and taste strange and unpredictable things. However, in today's business world, there are many unique habits of the people we encounter. For decades now, there has been an increased emphasis in

research and management practice in human capital investment. Four positive psychological capacities have been identified as best meeting the criteria of positive organizational behavior as positive, unique research-based, measurable, evolving, and manageable theories for the impact of performance in the workplace. There are workers who lack in showing reliable behavior in carrying out *tupoksi*, in other words if a worker is given responsibility is not immediately completed and workers who do not comply with working hours in carrying out their work activities. Leaders are required to understand the reliability of workers in the company organization in the hope of being able to design solutions to all problems faced. There are effective steps in seeing the reliability of a worker's work, namely through the implementation of an assessment of worker reliability, career opportunities, and the level of consistency of a worker to the company organization (Mukrimaa et al., 2016).

The 4.0 era is an era where opportunities await and challenges that must be faced because the industrial revolution 4.0 is more directed at automation. Where every human resource must be able to keep pace with the movement of automation so that it is not replaced with artificial intelligence. Creativity is needed to support the performance of human resources.

Creative humans have high initiative in changing a condition for the better and profitable company. Creativity is defined as the ability to imagine and generate new ideas by combining, changing or implementing existing ideas in ways that have not been thought of before. Creative ideas that are then processed through several stages to produce products or services or business models are called innovations (Zimmerer 2008: 57 in Lengkey et al., 2021). Creativity is not just luck but conscious hard work. Failure for creative people is simply a confounding variable for success. Creative people use the knowledge we all have and make possible leaps, they look at things in new ways. Creativity enables new discoveries in science and technology, as well as in all fields of human endeavor. One of the main conceptual constraints to the study of creativity is the notion of creativity as a trait inherited by extraordinarily gifted people or geniuses, creativity, besides being meaningful both for self-development and for community development is also one of the basic human needs, namely the need for self-realization as one of the highest needs for humans. One of the keys to increasing competitiveness in a company is to encourage the pace of innovation of a company in order to compete, both at the local, national, and global environmental levels. But these theoretical statements are not easy to apply at the empirical level. Innovation is not something simple nor is it something that can be obtained easily by every organization that has the same symptom, namely low competitiveness.

The results of Tanase's research (2020) suggest that innovation in organizations is positively and significantly influenced by the role of transformation leadership. This can also mean that innovation will grow and develop in the organization if the organizational leader can play a maximum role. Based on the background of this paper, the author is interested in the topic of innovation and HR development strategies and leaders should pay attention to it so that companies have human resources with high competitiveness in facing the challenges of changing business environments that are very fast in the future.

Without innovation in the company, the company will not be able to survive long. This is also shown by Man (2009) in his research which found that company performance is significantly influenced by innovation, especially in terms of reducing costs, changing product design, improving product manufacturing time cycles, developing product types, and organizational restructuring. It is very important for companies to always improve and develop innovation systems through innovative employees, procedures, processes, organizations, innovative organizational cultures, and innovative strategies (Mihic et al., 2015). Likewise, in order to make the company more competitive, the company should increase innovation more successfully, not only innovation in technology, research and development but also innovation in building communication relationships.

PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati is a long-established freight forwarder company located in the Kelapa Gading area with reliable human resources, competence supported by the role of talent management to produce innovation and creativity, improve quality performance.

Theoretical Foundation

Understanding Human Resource Management according to Bintoro and Daryanto (2017: 15) said that human resource management is a science or way of how to manage the relationship and role of resources (labor) owned by individuals efficiently and effectively and can be used optimally so that the common goals of the company, employees and society are maximized.

Competence

Moehariono (2015: 25) said that competence is a characteristic that underlies a person related to the effectiveness of individual performance in his job or the basic characteristics of individuals who have a causal relationship or as a cause-and-effect with criteria that are used as reference, effective or perform prime or superior at work or in certain situations. Innovation Suryana (2014: 54) revealed that innovation is the ability to apply creativity into something that can be implemented and provide added value to the resources owned. Innovation is the emergence of something new, for example in the form of a new idea, a new theory, a new hypothesis, or a new method for the management of an organization and business Creativity Zimmerman and Scarborough (2015: 36) reveal that creativity is the ability to develop new ideas and to find new ways of solving problems and finding opportunities. Mangkunegara Employee Performance (2016: 67), said that performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties with the responsibilities given to him.

Research conducted by Boston Consulting Group (2008) on several continents entitled "Creating People Advantage – How to address HR Challenges Worldwide through 2015" concluded several things: - Talented employees and leadership will become increasingly scarce resources - The average age of the workforce will get older, and now people tend to have fewer children Companies will move into global organizations. The emotional needs of employees will be more important than ever.

Another interesting data related to talent management is research from McKinsey (2001) which also reveals some interesting things:

1. The company's growth is limited due to insufficient proper talent.
2. The company lacks talented leaders.
3. In five years, the average company will lose 30% of its executive staff.
4. The error rate is high (40-50%) when employees of talented executives are hijacked from outside the company.
5. Two-thirds of employees have low to medium levels of trust in their top leadership. Three-quarters of their executives also said the same,
6. Employees state that company leadership is the main factor of job satisfaction, commitment and restraining factors in the company.
7. Employees most value the qualities of honesty and integrity in leaders
8. Only one percent of companies stated their succession was excellent, while two-thirds of them stated bad or mediocre. It can be seen that most organizations still do not have the ability to manage their talented employees, so there is a scarcity of leadership in many organizations.

Talent Management

Talent management has been defined with various descriptions in several versions. Among these are the following:

1. Identification, development and management of the talent portfolio i.e. the number, type and quality of employees who will achieve the company's strategic operational objectives effectively. The focus is on the importance of identifying an optimal talent portfolio, by calculating the impact of investments on the company's ability to achieve strategic and operational goals that match or exceed expectations. (Knez & Ruse, in Berger & Berger 2004, 231)
2. An integrated set of corporate initiatives aimed at improving the calibre, availability and flexible utilization of exceptionally capable (high potential) employee who can have a disproportionate impact on business performance (Smilansky, 2006).

This process should be integrated with the regular process of human resource management. The talent management process is designed to ensure that the business develops its competitive advantage through optimal utilization of a small group of individuals in key leadership positions. The two definitions above state that talent management is basically a combination of initiatives carried out by companies to create business excellence by optimizing their talented employees. The key is in the process of identifying, developing, and retaining talented employees to be able to continue to create business excellence for the company.

Talent management today is felt to be very important. Surveys from various world institutions and discourse from several authors identify that talented employees and leaders are increasingly difficult to find. The following excerpts will show why and how talent management and leadership development are seen as increasingly important. Research conducted by Boston Consulting Group (2008) on several continents entitled "*Creating People Advantage – How to address HR Challenges Worldwide through 2015*" concluded several things:

1. Talented people and leadership will become increasingly scarce resources
2. The average age of the workforce is getting older, and people are now more likely to have fewer children
3. Companies will move into global organizations
4. The emotional needs of employees will be more important than ever.

There are several things to consider in the development of talent management (Cheese, Thomas, & Craig, 2007):

1. Develop a *mindset* from top leadership to the bottom to see talented employees as a strategic issue and *human capital* as an intrinsic part of a business development strategy.
2. Recognize and grow distinction as one of the company's greatest assets. The ability to attract and work with diverse talent as a competitive advantage for the company
3. Build employee learning and skills development into organizational capabilities
4. Increase employee alignment and attachment to the organization and its mission
5. Ensure that all employees within the company, especially those at senior levels, see talent management as part of their work and responsibilities.

The company's talent management strategy should be adjusted to the company's vision, goals, and strategies, so that the company's human resources can dynamically adjust their competitive strategies to face changes in the business environment. (Carol, 2004; Jyotsna, 2007). Nowadays, the development of talent management itself has increased rapidly. The concept of Talent Based Human Resource Management (TBHRM) is slowly but surely considered by many practitioners as a more complete and comprehensive concept. Talent management can increase employee productivity and job satisfaction in achieving the expected business performance (Taleo, 2006; Michiel and Jan, 20205; Ian, 2007; Rakeshand Jyotsna, 2009)

Innovation

One of the factors that strengthen competition in business always involves innovation in various aspects of business operational activities. This is because the wants and needs of consumers can change quickly along with changes in environmental conditions and situations that exist around the lives of local people. Usually customers / consumers will try to find things that will satisfy their needs and desires. Very rapid changes from the consumer / customer side always need to be considered by the company and this is where the role of innovation that

continuously needs to be developed in the company both in an effort to pay attention to customer needs and desires and also the actions of competitors so that the company is not abandoned by its customers. This is supported by the results of research conducted by Mihic et al. (2015) which found that 72% of 36 companies stated that innovation is included in the top three priorities in a company's business operations. Therefore, today every organization expects its employees to be more creative, innovative and involved in handling this very rapid change in business environment (Echebiri, 2020). The results of research by Sundah et al. (2017) conducted on 44 smoked fish entrepreneurs in Manado City, North Minahasa Regency and Bitung City found that the main work attitude for entrepreneurs to be successful is discipline, honesty, perseverance, cooperation, creativity, dare to take risks, thrift and innovative. Innovation is an attitude that can be shown by employees to be able to develop and / or support the development of new ideas and strive for the use of new technology (Sundah, 2018)

Some experts have defined innovation in various statements. Mihic et al. (2015) stated that innovation is a tool to strengthen the competition of a company. Innovation is not a concept of a new idea, a new discovery or a development of a new market, but a picture of all these processes (Ernawati, 2019). Likewise, Baregheh et al. (2009) suggest that innovation is an organization's steps to change ideas in an effort to improve products, services, or processes as a way of competing to distinguish them from other competitors in the market. In addition, Nevado et al. (2016) stated that, "Creativity is the generation of ideas, design is the "formatting" of ideas and innovation is placing those forms in new and/or different contexts."

Suryana (2014: 54) revealed that innovation is the ability to apply creativity into something that can be implemented and provide added value to the resources owned. Innovation is the emergence of something new, for example in the form of a new idea, a new theory, a new hypothesis, or a new method for the management of an organization and business

The role of innovation in increasing creativity

It can also be concluded that the three things, namely creativity, design, and innovation, are three things that cannot be separated from one another where creativity is the generation of ideas, design is the formatting / formation of ideas, and innovation places these ideas in a new and / or different context. In fact, Hadiyati (2011) found that creativity and innovation have a partial and simultaneous effect on entrepreneurship, and innovation has a greater effect on entrepreneurship than creativity. Creativity is seen as the ability to develop new ideas and new ways of solving problems and finding opportunities, and at its core think of something new and different. While innovation is the ability to apply creativity in order to solve problems and find opportunities and at its core is the ability to do something new and different. However, the results of Hartini's (2012) research show that the company's attention to company innovation, both product innovation and process innovation is still very low. Only 10.6% of companies improve production processes, while judging from process innovation, only 8.1% have high process innovation. Similarly, with product quality, only 8.35% have high product quality. It is unfortunate if company leaders do not pay attention to innovation in business development.

Without innovation in the company, the company will not be able to survive long. This is also shown by Man (2009) in his research which found that company performance is significantly influenced by innovation, especially in terms of reducing costs, changing product design, improving product manufacturing time cycles, developing product types, and organizational restructuring. It is very important for companies to always improve and develop innovation systems through innovative employees, procedures, processes, organizations, innovative organizational cultures, and innovative strategies (Mihic et al., 2015). Likewise, in order to make the company more competitive, the company should increase innovation more successfully, not only innovation in technology, research and development but also innovation in building relationships with the company's target market (Nevado et al., 2016).

Human resource development strategy

HR management is an integrated part of business operational activities including being a business operational partner who understands business and HR management provides services for external and internal stakeholders more effectively (de Bruyn and Roodt, 2009). Each company has unique characteristics with limited resource availability and different problems and challenges. Thus, leaders will strive to solve the problems and challenges they face with the hope that they can achieve the vision, mission and goals of the company / organization that have been set. Based on this, the company / organization will design an HR development strategy based on innovation so that the achievement of the vision, mission, and goals can be more efficiently and effectively achieved. It can also be stated that the HR development strategy is an employee management policy that is integrated with the organization/company strategy and can be used to encourage organizational culture so that employees have values and quality competencies that are in accordance with the needs of achieving the vision, mission and goals and become a source of competitive advantage for individuals and companies / organizations. Innovation and HR development strategies are two things that cannot be separated from the activities of an organization / company to achieve its vision, mission and goals. Without innovation, the company will not be able to survive long in facing various challenges of changing science and technology and the business environment is very fast and will not become more efficient and effective in achieving the vision, mission and goals. However, without an HR development strategy, innovation will be unsystematic and unstructured and will not be directed at achieving the vision, mission and goals of the organization / company quickly and precisely. One of the basics of innovation-based HR development is to map/identify creative and innovative HR competencies in every work activity in the work unit that is their responsibility. Basic mapping is carried out objectively, fairly and of course in accordance with the needs of HR development and the needs of achieving the vision, mission and goals of the company / organization and corporate strategy. Cania (2014) supports this view by suggesting that companies / organizations need to be aware of the expectations desired by employees so that they can demonstrate their competence, be motivated and behave in a way that is necessary for the achievement of company / organizational goals.

Every company/organization will strive to create strong competitiveness in the market and strive to manage the available human resources in achieving the performance of the company/organization.

HR plays an important role in achieving the goals that a company / organization usually wants to achieve, namely reducing costs, achieving a certain level of sales, increasing the number of customers, increasing the percentage in market segmentation, improving product quality, creating innovative products, and increasing productivity (Cania, 2014).

DISCUSSION

PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati continues to encourage the development of its human resources through cooperation with various parties both from vendors, agents, ship owners in order to further advance PT Bhinneka Teknosejati's business. The human resources of PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati are expected to continue to advance the company and can become superior talents at the Freight Forwarder level.

The competence of PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati employees is reflected in performance, Good employee performance for PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati is to achieve its goals so that employee performance is something that deserves attention by Mrs. Fifi Aryanti as the leader of PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati. The performance of true PT Bhinneka Tekno employees is generally interpreted as success in carrying out a job. Employee performance is the result of work achieved by employees of PT Bhiineka Tekno Sejati. in carrying out the tasks assigned to him to achieve work targets.

Mrs. Fifi as the head of PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati, wants all employees to have competence so that:

1. Spirit of achievement to achieve work targets (*Achievement to work*)
2. Be thorough and have attention to work tasks (*Concern for order*)
3. Proactive (*Initiative*)
2. Have high curiosity (*Information seeking*)
3. Empathize with others (*Interpersonal understanding*)
4. Customer service orientation
5. Kemampuan komunikatif yang diplomatis dan persuasif (*Communicative Impact and influence*)

In connection with PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati oriented to customer satisfaction in all aspects from loading to unloading and goods are well received by customers. Because customer satisfaction is the main target of PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati which needs to be supported by the quality of employee performance.

PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati talent management is made to provide motivation, involve employees fully, and retain employees so that they can work better. This is what makes talent management a very important part of the company.

Talent management practices have become a strategic need for PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati. This pattern of practice is intended to optimize the role of human resources (HR) owned by PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati.

PT Bhinneka Tekno's talent management carried out by PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati also has many benefits (Fifi, 2023), namely:

1. Improve the recruitment process of new employees of PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati
2. Improve employee performance in PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati
3. Increase employee enthusiasm and motivation, especially new employees in the operational field who really need motivation, especially from seniors.
4. Strengthening employee relations with PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati.
5. Reduce employee *turnover*.
6. Study the risks of possible employees who want to resign.

With talent management, many employees of PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati who have worked for dozens of years continue to produce creativity and increasing innovation and problem solving goals where the risk of work is high in the operational field.

Every year PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati is always committed to employee commitment, more attached and feels the Company to be part of themselves.

PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati implements a reward system that can motivate employees where employees offer new ideas and they will take part in building a company/organization culture that values innovation, especially operations and marketing. Digital marketing talents are highly appreciated for creating content on PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati's social media. In addition, PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati rewards innovation by increasing salaries, bigger bonuses, or cash prizes. In practice, PT Bhinneka that proposing new ideas and creating an organizational culture that stimulates creativity and innovation in all areas of the company/organization should be encouraged through a combination of tangible and intangible awards.

The training activities carried out by PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati include *talent exchange*, *sharing digital learning platforms*, *benchmark learning programs*, the use of competency modules, *joint leadership programs*, and *sharing sessions conducted by third parties (inviting expert resource persons)*.

CONCLUSION

1. PT Bhinneka Tekno sejati always improves employee competence through training according to the field
2. PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati implements talent management to support employee creativity and placement according to competence
3. PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati appreciates the innovation of employees given to realize the vision
4. PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati also strives for employees to always be creative, especially in the operational and marketing fields which are the spearhead of the Company.
5. PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati always assesses the performance of its employees in order to be a reference for improvement and to set targets and objectives in operating.

Suggestion

1. PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati needs to maintain employee knowledge and invite academics to share knowledge about maintaining competence to continue to improve.
2. PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati should need to provide further education for its employees apart from training that improves competence
3. PT Bhinneka Tekno Sejati can continue to improve employee performance and maintain the good things that have been running within the company and still pay attention to outstanding employees in the company.
4. For future researchers, it is hoped that these results can be used as a reference for comparison in similar studies.

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